

TREATMENT OF DEGENERATIVE AND DYSTROPHIC CHANGES OF THE SPINE BASED ON MAGNETIC RESONANCE TOMOGRAPHY IDENTIFICATION

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Relevance of the work. In our republic, as a result of new developments in the field of medicine, modern diagnostic equipment with high diagnostic information such as magnetic resonance imaging (MRT) examination, which has become widely used in patient examination manuals, has become possible to correctly diagnose diseases of the lumbar spine. Osteochondrosis of the lumbar spine is widespread among diseases of the spine. The MRI examination method has the character of accurate diagnosis and makes it possible to identify the features of the vertebral column and spinal canal in frontal and sagittal sections without injecting a contrast agent. Pathogenetically-based treatment methods and surgical methods are used to permanently eliminate the discopedicular conflict situations caused by the complications of osteochondrosis of the lumbar vertebrae in patients.

Objectives and materials Degenerative and dystrophic changes were found in all patients of our follow-up, in one disc in some patients, and in two or more discs in the majority of patients. Degenerative changes are as follows: changes in the shape of the disc, reduction in height, blurring of the boundaries of the nucleus pulposus and attenuation of MRI signals. In the change of the disc due to dehydration, it is possible to distinguish 3 successive stages: a) pathological displacement of the pulpous nucleus in the intervertebral disc area; b) bulging of the disc; c) formation of disc herniation (sequestered disc herniation). It indicates the adequate adaptation of the spinal nerve roots located in the region of the spinal segment with stenosis.

Thus, surgical treatment of spinal canal stenosis allows to eliminate pain syndromes caused by stenosis. Some conditions that need to be clarified, namely, lumbar spinal canal stenosis and lumbar osteochondrosis together, although in the post-examination period are small, but new surgical methods aimed at preventing some acceleration of the observed interdisc degeneration process require future application. Determining the type of lumbar spinal canal stenosis and osteochondrosis of the lumbar spine and how many segments disc herniation is observed before the examination and choosing the right

examination method increases the efficiency of the examination and the weight of the obtained positive results.

Based on the excellent orthopedic-clinical and diagnostic examinations of 140 patients under our supervision, we performed operations using the following surgical methods:

In 103 (73.6%) patients, since osteochondrosis of lumbar vertebrae and disc herniation were observed, we used arcotomy + discectomy + foraminotomy diagnostic method.

In 24 (17.1%) patients, hemilaminectomy + discectomy + foraminotomy + spinal canal reconstruction were observed due to osteochondrosis of lumbar vertebrae, disc herniation, stenosis of the spinal canal, ossification of the yellow ligament.

In 13 (9.3%) patients, osteochondrosis of the lumbar vertebrae, disc herniation, circular stenosis of the spinal canal, hypertrophy of the yellow ligament, osteophytes of the vertebral body, and hypertrophy of the joint surfaces were observed.

In conclusion, from the analysis of MRI scans of 140 patients before the operation, it was found that it is necessary to accurately diagnose the pathological center of the spine in which segment of the spine is located, the compression factor, the total volume of the spinal canal, the percentage occupied in the frontal and axial section, and to perform the necessary small-scale operations and , makes it possible to develop and base instructions for the operation.

Thus, in the surgical treatment of osteochondrosis of the lumbar vertebrae, taking into account its orthopedic features, the performed small-scale surgical methods have the ability to eliminate all factors that cause discopedicular conflicts. In these operations, the anatomic structure of the vertebrae is not damaged to a large extent. For this reason, the operated segment of the spine retains its orthopedic properties.